

Major traits of Gan wan nuo 5, Rice Research Institute of China, 1992.

Trait	Value
Brown rice (%)	79.7
Milled rice recovery (%)	69.7
Head rice (%)	58.2
Kernel length(mm)	5.5
L-W ratio	2.2
Alkali spreading value	6
Gel consistency (mm)	100
Amylose content (%)	1.6
Protein content of head rice (%)	8.0

Gan wan nuo 5 has a strong, 120-cm-long stem. It has a growth duration of 135-140 d in single-cropped areas. The variety has high yield potential with good irrigation and good management.

Gan wan nuo 5 has a 1,000-grain weight of 25.3 g, panicle length of 24.9 cm, and 141 filled grains panicle⁻¹. The variety is used for making stuffed dumplings, cakes, and sweet wines.

Gan wan nuo 5 is widely planted and is spreading quickly in southern and central China. A total area of 70,000 ha was devoted to the crop from 1992 to 1998. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

Inheritance of resistance to bacterial leaf blight in differential rice variety Asominori

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Asominori is one of the international differentials used for testing the pathogenicity of the bacterial leaf blight (BLB) pathogen, *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae*. It has been one of the varieties most resistant to BLB in Japan since its release in 1973. Extensive testing under the JIRCAS and YAAS collaborative research project on rice genetic resources between 1994 and 1996 showed that Asominori has stable resistance to BLB in both indica and

japonica rice-growing areas in Yunnan, China. Hence, Asominori is considered a useful source of durable resistance to BLB. We found that Asominori has an allele of the *Xa1* locus on chromosome 4 for BLB resistance, although it has been reported to harbor *Xa17* independent from *Xa1*.

First, we found that Asominori grain showed a positive reaction to phenol solution, even though almost all japonica varieties in Japan have been reported to show negative reactions. The trait was inherited as a monogenic character in F₂ plants between Asominori and varieties Kogyoku and St No. 1, which showed a negative reaction to phenol. No segregant had a negative reaction to phenol in the F₃ seeds of each F₂ plant (n = 240) between Asominori and a near-isogenic line of Taichung 65 with a marker *Ph*, suggesting that Asominori had the *Ph* gene on chromosome 4.

To further test the association between phenol reaction of grains and resistance to BLB, we screened 16 varieties or breeding lines in the pedigree of Asominori. Only Saikai 85 displayed a positive phenol reaction

and resistance to BLB isolates. None of the other 15 varieties/lines (Tadukan, Senbonasahi, Pi No. 2, Saikai 97, Jikkoku, Zensho 26, Benisengoku, Chukyoasahi, Ojo, Saikai 59, Chujo 2, Norin 22, Tozan 38, Shinyamabuki, and Sachikaze) showed either of the two traits.

Second, BLB resistance of the varieties and their hybrids was evaluated by the clipping inoculation method around the heading stage in a rice field. Table 1 shows the reaction of parental varieties, F₁, and F₂ plants. All the F₁ plants were resistant to BLB isolates T7174 (race I), H9153 (race II-2), and H75304 (race V), which were collected in Japan. The segregation ratios in the F₂ populations were 3 (resistant): 1 (susceptible), suggesting that BLB resistance in Asominori was controlled by a single dominant gene. The BLB resistance gene of Asominori and *Ph* was closely linked with a recombination value of 2.4% in the coupling phase; all the segregation ratios were consistent with the genetic model (Table 2). This value was also consistent with the 2.8% recombination between *Ph* and *Xa1* reported earlier

Table 1. Segregation for reaction to BLB isolates in F₂ populations between Asominori, Kogyoku, and St No. 1.

Variety or cross combination	Number of plants for each reaction to T7174, H9153, and H75304 ^a				Goodness of fit to 3:1	
	RRR	RSR	SSS	Total	χ^2	Probability
Asominori	15	0	0	15		
Kogyoku	0	15	0	15		
St No. 1	0	0	15	15		
Asominori/Kogyoku (F ₁)	3	0	0	3		
Asominori/St No.1 (F ₁)	5	0	0	5		
Asominori/Kogyoku (F ₂)	296	94	0	390	0.168	0.6-0.7
Asominori/St No.1 (F ₂)	50	0	24	74	2.180	0.1-0.2
Asominori/St No.1 (F ₂)	265 ^b	0	73 ^b	338	2.087	0.1-0.2

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible, RRR stands for resistant reaction to three BLB isolates used, respectively. ^bInoculated by isolates T7174 and H75304 only.

Table 2. Linkage relationship between BLB resistance and a genetic marker *Ph* in F₂ populations between Asominori, Kogyoku, and St No. 1.

Cross combination (F ₂)	Segregation mode ^a				Recombination value ± SE (%) ^b	Goodness of fit	
	AB	Ab	aB	ab		χ^2	Probability
Asominori/Kogyoku	292	4	5	89	2.37 ± 0.78	0.335	0.9-1.0
Asominori/St No. 1	49	1	1	23	2.48 ± 1.83	2.254	0.5-0.6

^aA = a dominant gene for BLB resistance in Asominori; B = *Ph* gene for phenol reaction. ^bWeighted mean of recombination values is 2.4% in a coupling phase.

using Japanese and IRRI varieties. Furthermore, we did not observe a segregant susceptible to isolates T7174 and H75304 in the F₂ plants (n = 390) and to isolate T7174 in the F₃ (n = 880) from Asominori/Kogyoku harboring the resistance gene *Xa1*. Thus, we concluded that Asominori had an allele at the *Xa1* locus controlling resistance to the three BLB isolates.

Another allele at the *Xa1* locus, *Xa1-h*, was previously reported in IRRI varieties IR28, IR29, and IR30. The *Xa1-*

h allele differs from the *Xa1* of Kogyoku in that *Xa1-h* shows high resistance to BLB race I at both the seedling and adult stages, whereas *Xa1* shows unstable resistance at the seedling stage and high resistance at the adult stage. The resistance of IR28, IR29, IR30, and Kogyoku to BLB race V was controlled not by the alleles of *Xa1*, but by those of *Xa12* closely linked with *Xa1*. The allele of Asominori on the *Xa1* locus, however, displayed high resistance to races I and V at both the seedling and

adult stages. Therefore, we tentatively designated the *Xa1* allele responsible for the high resistance in Asominori as *Xa1-as(t)*.

Asominori with *Xa1-as(t)* has been highly resistant to BLB for more than 20 yr whereas Kogyoku and Asakaze with *Xa1* showed a breakdown in resistance. We are developing near-isogenic lines on *Xa1-as(t)* to clarify the relationship between the durability of Asominori's resistance and the pleiotropic effects of *Xa1-as(t)*. ■

Potential sources of resistance against RGSV-2 in wild rice germplasm

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IRRI varieties released after IR28 possess a source of resistance from *Oryza nivara* against rice grassy stunt virus, RGSV-1 strain. Although the resistance seems to be durable, the presence of a resistance-breaking strain, RGSV-2 (Hibino et al 1985), raises concerns about possible outbreaks if no new sources of resistance are found. Since 1985, about 12,000 accessions have been screened against the two strains, but no suitable resistance sources have been identified (Koganezawa 1994). Thus, during 1996-97, a collection of wild rice species was screened for RGSV-2 using the standard mass-screening cage method (Ling et al 1970) and some accessions, which showed low visual scores, were evaluated further using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

Based on ELISA scores, several *O. officinalis* accessions from the Philippines, Indonesia, Malaysia, Brunei, and Thailand, *O. minuta* from the Philippines, and *O. punctata* from Nigeria showed 0% infection (Table 1). Because all these species are also resistant to the three brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes, however, it is difficult to predict whether the resistance is targeted against the virus or the vector. Two *O. nivara* accessions

Table 1. Mass screening of wild rice species for resistance to RGSV-2.

Accession no.	Wild rice species	Origin	Biotype			ELISA	
			BPH 1	BPH 2	BPH 3	n	Score % infection
100115	<i>O. brachyantha</i>	Guinea				22	14 64
100139	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Africa				19	18 95
100153	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Africa				34	31 91
100170	<i>O. latifolia</i>	Costa Rica	3	3	3	25	20 80
100180	<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	1	3	3	21	1 5
100882	<i>O. australiensis</i>	Unknown	1	3	3	26	19 73
100890	<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	7	7	9	24	16 67
100937	<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	1	3	3	4	1 25
100956	<i>O. latifolia</i>	India	3	5	7	23	20 87
100961	<i>O. glumaepatula</i>	Cuba				19	4 21
101074	<i>O. officinalis</i>	Philippines	1	3	3	17	0 0
101089	<i>O. minuta</i>	Philippines	3	3	3	26	0 0
101234	<i>O. brachyantha</i>	Sierra Leone	3	3	3	23	2 9
101330	<i>O. punctata</i>	Nigeria				2	0 0
101408	<i>O. punctata</i>	Ghana	3	1	3	25	20 80
101417	<i>O. punctata</i>	Kenya	1	5	9	17	5 29
101466	<i>O. meridionalis</i>	Australia	9	9	9	32	28 88
102569	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Liberia				24	21 88
103437	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	9	9	9	6	6 100
103801	<i>O. officinalis</i>	Indonesia	1	1	1	6	0 0
103888	<i>O. punctata</i>	Tanzania	3	3	1	25	4 16
103889	<i>O. punctata</i>	Tanzania	3	3	1	28	24 86
103896	<i>O. punctata</i>	Tanzania	3	3	1	5	4 80
104059	<i>O. punctata</i>	Nigeria	1	3	1	28	0 0
104064	<i>O. punctata</i>	Nigeria	1	5	1	19	3 16
104672	<i>O. officinalis</i>	Malaysia	3	3	3	31	0 0
104974	<i>O. punctata</i>	Kenya				9	7 78
105100	<i>O. officinalis</i>	Brunei	1	1	1	33	29 88
105102	<i>O. officinalis</i>	Brunei	1	1	1	21	0 0
105145	<i>O. latifolia</i>	Colombia				38	32 84
105227	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Thailand				6	6 100
105240	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Thailand				14	14 100
105250	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Thailand				29	27 93
105303	<i>O. meridionalis</i>	Australia				25	22 88
105327	<i>O. nivara</i>	India				11	10 91
105365	<i>O. officinalis</i>	Thailand				25	0 0
105417	<i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka				23	17 74
105425	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Sri Lanka				16	1 6
105662	<i>O. glumaepatula</i>	Brazil				21	19 90
105823	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Thailand				14	3 21
105845	<i>O. nivara</i>	Thailand				13	7 54
105846	<i>O. nivara/O. sativa</i>	Thailand				25	17 68
105848	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Thailand				9	6 67
105855	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh				31	22 71
105891	<i>O. rufipogon</i>	Bangladesh				10	8 80
105893	<i>O. nivara/O. sativa</i>	Bangladesh				30	27 90
105	TN1	Taiwan				40	40 100